

CREATION OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING MATERIALS USING MICROSOFT WORD PROGRAM

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Annotation. The article shows the influence of electronic educational resources on the development of educational material, forms and methods of organizing students' activities.

Key words: methodological teaching system, modern information educational environment, electronic educational resources, learning objectives, learning content, forms of learning, teaching methods, teaching aids.

Information technologies are being introduced into all spheres of our society, including education.

Educational and methodological support of the educational process consists of complementary elements, the central place among which is occupied by electronic learning tools, within which electronic educational materials can be separately distinguished.

Electronic educational resources are educational materials that are reproduced using electronic devices.

In the most general case, EER includes educational videos and sound recordings, for playback of which a household tape recorder or CD player is sufficient.

The most modern and effective electronic educational resources for education are reproduced on a computer. It is on such resources that we will focus our attention.

Sometimes, in order to highlight this subset of EER, they are called digital educational resources (DER), meaning that the computer uses digital recording/playback methods. However, audio/video compact discs (CDs) also contain recordings in digital formats, so introducing a separate term and abbreviation DOR does not provide any significant benefit. Therefore, it is better to use the general term "electronic" and the abbreviation EOR.

So, here and further we consider electronic educational resources that require a computer to play.

An electronic textbook is an independent educational electronic manual for complex purposes, which ensures the continuity and completeness of the didactic cycle of the learning process, and the student's information and search activities. The electronic textbook contains theoretical and practical materials in accordance with the curriculum, using elements of multimedia technologies.

Educational electronic publication (EEP) is an electronic publication containing systematized material on the relevant scientific and practical field of knowledge, ensuring creative and active acquisition by students of knowledge, skills and abilities in this field. OEI should be distinguished by a high level of execution and artistic design, completeness of information, quality of methodological tools, quality of technical execution, clarity, logic and consistency of presentation. OEI cannot be reduced to a paper version without losing its didactic properties.

The Microsoft Word processor is a powerful tool for creating documents of various purposes and complexity. In particular, it allows you to create certain types of electronic educational materials.

The Microsoft Office suite of applications is a set of application tools designed to automate office work. The Microsoft Office suite of applications includes a number of applications that perform a specific function and can work either separately or together.

The GUI of MS Word uses various controls grouped together using an object called the "ribbon".

The Ribbon is a strip at the top of the screen that contains all the main sets of commands, grouped by topic on separate tabs and groups. It is designed to make commands easier to access and consists of tabs associated with specific goals or objects. Each tab, in turn, consists of several groups of interconnected controls. Compared to the menus and toolbars used in previous versions of MS Word, the Ribbon holds significantly more content - buttons, collections, dialog box elements, etc.

Microsoft has created the Microsoft Office suite of applications taking into account modern technologies used in everyday life. Today, the difference between office workers working at home and in the office is disappearing. People choose for themselves where, how and what to work. Many business people need to work with information not only at home or in the office, but also when going somewhere on business or on the road. These processes require businessmen to have new capabilities to ensure information security.

There are several of these important ideas in the Office suite of applications and its accompanying software suite. One of them is the ability to process documents using lightweight versions of Word, PowerPoint, Excel and OneNote using dedicated web applications anywhere in the world. At the same time, Office features can also be used on mobile smartphone devices running on the Windows Mobile platform (environment).

Editing a MS Word document involves adjusting the size of the document and the size of its fields, correcting spelling errors in the text of the document, inserting additions, setting line spacing, changing the type of headings (heading, sub-heading) means changing according to the requirements of the printing house by installing, placing a letterhead, writing in capitals letters, formatting document text and performing similar actions.

The ability to embed objects of various types into Microsoft Word documents, as well as the ability to establish hypertext links, allows you to create fragments of multimedia resources.

The English word “multimedia” means “many ways”.

Representing learning objects in multiple ways, e.g. using graphics, photos, videos, animations and sound. Using everything that a person is able to perceive with the help of sight and hearing.

For example: a well-known multimedia player is called multimedia because it can play photographs, videos, sound recordings, and text in turn.

When we talk about multimedia ESM. This refers to the ability to simultaneously reproduce on a computer screen and in sound a certain set of objects presented in various ways.

The main formats are Word document format and RTF format, which can be converted to HTML and PDF hypertext formats if necessary. The advantages of electronic educational materials are:

- mobility;
- accessibility due to the development of computer networks;
- the ability to quickly update educational material;
- speed of adjustment; o ease of selection and arrangement;
- the ability to illustrate various processes and phenomena in dynamics;
- large volume of material;
- the ability to gradually accumulate material;
- ease of replication;
- relieving teachers of a number of labor-intensive and frequently repeated operations to present educational information;

- the ability to expand the regular textbook
- adaptation to the pace of the student's work, facilitating the search for necessary information; the opportunity to study educational material and perform practical work at home;
- independence of the quality of stored material from the intensity of its use;
- compact in area and volume.

The new generation EER is an open educational modular multimedia system.

ESM allows you not only to independently study the description of objects, processes, phenomena, but also to work with them interactively, solve problem situations and connect the acquired knowledge from life.

Students are involved in a fascinating process of learning, where they independently obtain information, analyze it, exchange opinions, and draw conclusions.

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